

IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS: CONTENT, ESSENCE AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS

Q.B. Panjiyev

Head of “Music Education” Department, International Nordic University; Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Acting Professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17861705>

Abstract. *This article describes the existing pedagogical conditions, content, and essence, as well as some methodological foundations for improving the professional training of future music teachers.*

Keywords: *music, education, pedagogical, methodological, theoretical, foundations, training, professional, musical characteristics, conditions, mechanism.*

Introduction

It is important to note that solving the problem of professionally oriented education for students in the field of music education in higher education institutions of our country involves not only improving specific aspects of the educational and pedagogical process but also fundamentally reconsidering its conceptual foundations. The essence of this educational process primarily consists of determining the professional training of the future teacher and defining the content, forms, and methods of improving professional-pedagogical training within the overall education system.

Taking into account the conclusions of scholars and specialists in the field (V.V. Kraevskiy, M. Skatkin, and others), it should be noted that solving this problem can only be achieved by scientifically understanding and substantiating the professional training of students in the music education program as a specific didactic object and improving this process in higher education institutions. According to pedagogical theory and requirements, the logical basis of such substantiation involves moving from theoretically representing the object (professional training) to constructing a clear system of its content, forms, and means.

The general theoretical idea of improving professional training through Uzbek folk songs can be recognized as the essence of the scientific-pedagogical substantiation conducted in this study. At the theoretical level, the results of such substantiation are strictly structured special scientific analyses, including “content,” “tasks,” “forms,” and “methods.” The final goal of the research is to determine the content, theoretical foundations, methodological approaches, and tools of professional training of future music teachers through Uzbek folk singing, as well as the content of the educational activity together with its legal component.

Main Part

In philosophical and general professional pedagogical methodology, any specific scientific research should be based on methodological foundations and guidelines. This, in turn, defines logic and research methods and allows predicting its results (theory, content, logical and substantiated components, etc.). From this, in solving the research problem, the author proposes the following initial approaches as a starting position, which consider a comprehensive socio-pedagogical and didactic analysis of the object:

a) social status requirements related to the social life and practice of the population;
b) in the context of a comprehensive system of professional training of future music teachers.

b) To take into account, within the higher music-pedagogical education system, the specific conditions and characteristics of professional training content and activity through Uzbek folk songs.

The content of professional training for future music teachers is primarily determined by social demand, pedagogical theory, and practical needs, and it functions as a specific form of expression. Improving the foundations of professional training of future music teachers reflects one of the most important trends in the field of higher music education pedagogy: creating optimal conditions for their creative development as specialists in the future and enhancing professionally oriented methodological thinking. Music pedagogy, as an integral part of education, represents a dynamic system that fulfills a number of specific tasks and constitutes one of the most important components of professional training.

When defining the essence of the main tasks in professional training of future music teachers, it is important, first of all, to consider the external manifestation, content, form, and method of the object within the system of relations. By relying on its general philosophical meaning, and simultaneously from a socio-pedagogical perspective, it is crucial for the holistic process of improving the professional training of the music teacher, influencing the comprehensive development of the teacher's personality including motivational-value, intellectual, and activity spheres.

During professional training, the specialist's thinking and work style are rapidly restructured, and creative professional potential is enriched. Within the music education system, professional training mainly serves a cognitive function, helping bachelor students actively acquire knowledge in science and in various genres of vocal art. This knowledge contributes to their understanding of social-professional and personal value. Based on this knowledge, future specialists acquire the necessary ways to understand and transform musical-pedagogical reality, gaining experience in applying it creatively in practice.

The integrated approach implemented in professional training helps establish interdisciplinary connections, which in turn creates completely new conditions for systematizing and expanding the thinking experience of future music teachers. Music-pedagogical education not only ensures the application of professional knowledge accumulated in the future specialist's experience across various fields of science and music art (aesthetics, pedagogy, musicology, performance, theory, practice, etc.), but also plays a determinative role in consistently understanding the essence of this knowledge and studying professionally significant problems with a didactic and systematic holistic approach.

Different levels of professional-oriented knowledge (pedagogical, professional, scientific, specific) guide the synthesis of ideas and professional training of future music teachers within the multi-faceted pedagogical support of music education (school - education - upbringing) and related aspects. In this context, specific empirical facts and phenomena in music lessons are understood not only professionally, but also methodologically through the prism of general laws of the musical-pedagogical process, based on scientific and theoretical foundations.

Cognitively oriented activity is aimed at expanding the professional experience of future music teachers, improving various aspects of their work, and developing their aspirations. During practical exercises in folk singing, future specialists deepen their personal and practical attitudes

toward musical-pedagogical concepts, curricula, manuals, art, and various innovative processes in general and music pedagogy.

Moreover, in the minds of future music teachers, under the direct influence of professional training, there is a “re-evaluation” of real musical professional knowledge, skills, abilities, and competencies, which often determines the personal and creative path manifested by the teacher through functional and pragmatic approaches. In such cases, the ability to analyze and perform a musical work using artistic and creative authority is realized from a broader perspective by the music teacher. Establishing moral and personal connections with bachelor students, enriching their artistic, musical, and social experience, is an essential condition.

During professional training, future music teachers refer to various levels of methodological knowledge, primarily based on the needs of musical and pedagogical practice. They become aware of the highly complex combination of issues and problems, as well as the multi-level conceptual understanding of theoretical and methodological problems in music pedagogy achieved in pedagogical, psychological, musical, aesthetic, and other professional training processes. This significantly expands the professional and cognitive interests of future music teachers and fosters the continuous acquisition of new knowledge from various fields of science and art. The pedagogical conditions for improving and implementing professional training have been defined as follows:

- Students’ possession of skills in vocal and instrumental performance, their knowledge of music theory, and the development of abilities, skills, and performance competencies;
- Adequacy of educational-methodological and material-technical support, as well as the creation of conditions for the use of advanced digital technologies in teaching;
- Monitoring and self-monitoring of students’ mastery of curricula, independent learning, and improvement of performance skills individually, in ensembles, and in groups.

The description of professional training refers to its specific motivating influence on the personal, artistic, cognitive, value-oriented thinking, and activity of future music teachers. During the process of forming methodological professional musical culture, each student is given the right to choose methods of knowledge and activity that best correspond to their general and professional individual-personal desires and capabilities. Based on a personal approach, the content and process of professional training aim primarily to awaken the future music teacher’s creative self-awareness, develop their moral and spiritual world, and foster the ability to self-reflect, creating optimal conditions in the classroom.

Naturally, the process of improving professional training brings significant changes. The integrated nature of teaching and educational processes involves elevating this process to metaphysical, reproductive, dialectical, and creative levels. Another important aspect of professional training sessions is their heuristic nature. The process of developing the creative-professional thinking of bachelor students is primarily determined by the nature of methodological knowledge, general principles, and the activity methods characterized by pedagogical mobility. According to the experienced scholar H. Santulo, “strong heuristic ability is associated with generating effective ideas, developing research strategies, and stimulating theoretical synthesis.”

The mechanism of revealing and assimilating this knowledge can be compared to search and research activity, including stages such as presenting the problems within the content, searching for solutions, and analyzing the results of such searches. General methodological knowledge always encourages the music teacher to engage in holistic thinking, primarily focusing on its creative components (forecasting, analyzing, reasoning, generalizing, etc.). Stimulating

these components in the process of professional training is always linked to the student's individual creative experience, providing an opportunity to reveal their strongest personal qualities.

The heuristic function of professional training also lies in expanding the range and "comparative weight" of professional knowledge. Here, knowledge from various scientific and artistic fields is included in the independent research and creative activities of future music teachers aimed at improving professional training through Uzbek folk songs, often encompassing the content of specific disciplines. Moreover, during professional training, it is not only important to acquire knowledge and skills but also to understand the mechanism of mastering them, which is crucial for the effective development of professional competencies.

For this reason, the future music teacher, in this process, functions both as a researcher studying specific professional problems and as a participant who constantly reflects on the logic of their own inquiry and methodologically understands the truths of music pedagogy. This is realized in a special form of theoretical activity – "reflection" in social pedagogy. For understanding this issue more deeply, let us attempt an explanation. Reflection in thinking and activity, as a value-oriented and reflexive approach, was emphasized by G.F. Hegel, who noted that the result of any search activity must always be understood simultaneously with the process of obtaining it. Today, the category of professional thinking is widely examined at all levels of scientific thought and is one of the key factors in shaping the general and professional thinking culture of specialists, as well as the creative components of their personality, especially in the context of globalization.

The concept of reflection in the methodology of music pedagogy is one of the central issues, fundamentally deriving from the general philosophical definition. Here it manifests in various senses, including: "the principle of thinking, its understanding and direction toward application"; "studying knowledge itself, critically analyzing its content and methods of cognition"; and "revealing the inner structure and characteristics of the human spiritual world." This general interpretation is further specified in pedagogy as: "reflection as knowledge of pedagogical science" (M.N. Skatkin); "the researcher's self-awareness and thinking about their own activity" (V.V. Kraevskiy); and "the teacher's self, inner world, capabilities, as well as how they are perceived by communication partners, primarily students, reconstructing the internal world of the partners subjectively" (V.I. Zagvyazinskiy). Defining tasks and conditions links the formation of professional culture in future music teachers with strengthening reflection in teaching, helping students understand their knowledge, practical actions, logic, and tools.

Based on these concepts, in the process of professional training, the "self-reflection" of future music teachers is characterized by specific features (mainly musical) and operates as the cognitive and practical process of understanding and transforming musical and pedagogical truth. The reflective-heuristic nature of professional training manifests primarily through its dialogic quality. Here, the future music teacher simultaneously engages in several practices and "communication." Dialogue involves analyzing one's own activity, reflecting on the objective and subjective significance of music-pedagogical problems, and the necessary knowledge to study them; internal dialogue expresses a unique performative skill in interaction with participants in musical and music-pedagogical processes (professors, accompanists, performers, students).

The presence of dialogic processes in professional training sessions helps future music teachers develop a creative, methodologically oriented thinking style, whose main characteristics include "pre-reflection," empathy, and a creative approach. The heuristic effect of professional training within the holistic process of music-pedagogical education ensures that professional

knowledge and methods acquired by specialists are valuable in other disciplines and in creative activities, including specialized lessons. Methodological analysis plays a special role here: future music teachers must experience all forms of research and creative activity (e.g., writing reports and presentations within research and development, understanding artistic and performance issues, addressing musical and theoretical problems, and conducting experimental-practical tasks in higher pedagogical education).

Providing professional knowledge and activity methods across various areas confirms, on one hand, the didactic significance of this knowledge and, on the other hand, demonstrates their role in developing the creative abilities of future specialists. The heuristic aspect of improving the professional training of future music teachers is the concretization of its content, that is, the conceptualization of the future teacher's thinking. Based on professional scientific research (V.N. Rostorguev, B.C. Shubinskiy, and others), this process involves developing not only knowledge of specific nominative facts but also attitudes, knowledge, and abilities that provide a scientifically grounded basis for theoretical or professional hypotheses, ideas, and concepts at a personal level in a given professional field. Its content and process aim to develop this type of thinking and to restore the social authority of the "authorial" approach in pedagogy, specifically in music education.

In the higher education system, the nature of the educational process as one of the indicators of the heuristic effect of professional training in the education of future music teachers is, to some extent, a live collaborative process between teacher and student, serving as a special form of equal, moral, and creative dialogue. The discussed function of professional training is also expressed in its significant influence on selecting pedagogical forms and methods and in defining the need to create conditions for the creative interaction of future music teachers. The professional training process involves not only equipping future music teachers with professional knowledge and creative experience in applying it but also forming a value-oriented attitude toward understanding and transforming musical-pedagogical reality. This training impacts the moral-value aspects of the future teacher's consciousness and activity, fulfilling its axiological function. Its essence lies in that the content of professional training serves students not only as a professional reflection of various events and processes in musical and pedagogical reality but also as a foundation for forming a personal-value attitude toward this aspect of their professional and creative activity.

In conclusion, it is important to note that in forming such attitudes, methodological knowledge, which reflects broad human socio-spiritual experience plays a crucial role. Knowledge in various fields of science and vocal art, as well as expert insights, helps future music teachers understand specific professional problems. At the same time, music education allows graduates to access the moral and personal world of the future music teacher (philosophy, pedagogy, psychology, music theory, vocal and instrumental performance, musicology, folklore studies, ethnomusicology). It mainly involves discovering moral-aesthetic and related aspects. The integration of thoughts and feelings that occurs in this process positively influences the improvement of the future music teacher's moral, didactic criteria and needs.

Conclusion

Understanding the essential and fundamental value of methodological knowledge allows future music teachers to comprehend their own life and professional experience in the context of the social daily life, cultural, and pedagogical practices of society, and to engage with it in their professional activity. Naturally, such professional knowledge is personally significant for the future music teacher and serves not only to enhance scientific understanding but also to improve

professional training in a humanistic direction. In the professional training process, the fulfillment of this condition is ensured through specific pedagogical forms and tools (creative pedagogical games, problem-based dialogic discussions) relying on personal and creative approaches.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullin E.B. Theory and practice of music education in general education schools. Moscow, 1983.
2. Ibrohimov O.A. Uzbek folk music creativity (Methodical recommendations, Part 1). Tashkent, 1994, P. 62.
3. Ibrohimjonova G.A., Yuldoshev U.Yu. Music Theory. Textbook. Tashkent, 2017.
4. Panjiyev Q.B. Improving the professional training of future music teachers through uzbek folk songs. Monography, 2022, P.202.
5. Panjiyev Q.B. Methods of Teaching Music. Textbook. Tashkent, 2023, P.306.